

INNOVATIVE METHODS AND SCIENCE TEACHING

Mrs. Seema. P.V

Lecturer, College of Education, Srinivas University, Mangalore

Email: vaiseema@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Science is one of the core subject which leads to technological advancement of the country. Science plays an important role in education because of its relevance to life and society. Use of computers and ICT revolutionized teaching-learning process which improves the quality of education. UNESCO (2002) emphasizes that teacher education institute should prepare new generation of teachers to use ICT effectively in their teaching process. Teacher should use innovative methods of teaching keeping in view the present needs and technological advancement of the society and help the students to involve themselves in teaching learning process to make them to understand scientific knowledge and their application to the fullest maximum extent. Teaching science through innovative methods as interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary help to attain knowledge skills and attitudes required to compete with the global standards. The country aspires every education system to give young people the basic skills required for present society and enable them to solve problems logically. To develop such skills it is important that science education should be given attention in our school curriculum considering the benefits from it. This demands innovative approaches in science teaching to make science discipline more innovative and enable students to cope up with modern society.

Key words: Innovative, Interdisciplinary, Multidisciplinary, Curriculum

Introduction:

Science is one of the core subjects. It is a structured and systematic form of knowledge, whereas technology is the practical application of scientific knowledge .Science as a discipline develops skills such as experimentation, observation, measurement, problem solving in logical form. The development of country depends on the quality of science and technological education that the individual receives. Science and technology played a very important role in the development of individual as well as society.

Science as a discipline helps the individual to equip themselves with the needs of modern society.

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This is not possible if the teacher uses traditional methods of teaching such as lecture method, memorization of facts etc because such methods give information about bookish knowledge and the students become the passive listeners moreover science curriculum is overloaded with knowledge. Content is not organized, no colorful pictures or graphical representation and the curriculum is uninteresting to the students. The traditional textbooks are not helpful to develop scientific attitudes. So to develop curiosity, critical thinking, scientific attitudes and abilities there is a serious need of trained teachers to use innovative method of teaching and reconstructing curriculum which is based on innovative techniques such as interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary.

Multidisciplinary curriculum is studying a topic from the viewpoint of more than one discipline and solving a problem using a different disciplinary approach (Klaassen, 2018). For example, reducing the CO₂ emissions from a car can be achieved by studying how to develop fuel chemistry or by studying how to improve car engine performance.

The instruction may be organized on fundamental issues common to the three academic disciplines instead of teaching the students in a disjointed and unconnected manner. Examples of the multidisciplinary approach can be illustrated by Integrated Social Studies (Geography, Political Science, Sociology, Psychology), and Integrated Science (Biology, Chemistry, and Physics) as reflected in the junior secondary curriculum in Botswana. The use of the multidisciplinary approach in instruction can equally be referred to as the integrated approach.

More importantly, multidisciplinary instruction allows for the use of literacy activities. This is especially beneficial in language teaching and learning. Through the implementation of read-aloud, guided reading and independent reading, students are provided with multiple opportunities to develop content knowledge. In English, storytelling can be an important avenue for constructing knowledge in Science, Art and Social Studies and so on.

The multidisciplinary approach requires that teachers apply various modern methods, techniques and means in their teaching. The curriculum content dealing with natural sciences needs to be integrated, and for this we need to apply a multidisciplinary approach aimed at achieving Clarity. Multidisciplinary instruction is an approach that thoughtfully incorporates and connects key concepts and skills from many disciplines into the presentation of a single unit. Langa and Yost (2007:65) add that it is a methodology to help students make connections. Mathison and Maston

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(1989) observe that multidisciplinary instruction helps students connect and use information that they have learned from one discipline to address the problem at hand.

Furthermore, multidisciplinary instruction provides learners with a more comprehensive learning that is rich and interesting. The fact that the different disciplines borrow knowledge from each other potentially makes the classroom amusing and thought provoking. This is supported by Bansford, Brown and Cockin(2002) when they state that integrating learning through multiple disciplines provides students with a more comprehensive learning experience that unifies, and a greater understanding than that which could be obtained by examining the parts separately.

Moreover, the use of the multidisciplinary approach permits the teacher to combine a variety of methods, techniques and technological devices. In fact, it is believed that multidisciplinary teaching gets the whole school, teachers, parents and community involved. This is because it facilitates team and collaborative activities. Teachers share classroom activities, worksheets and resources with each other to facilitate their students’ learning. The parents also get involved as they work collaboratively with teachers to address students’ learning needs and issues. Students also learn collaboratively as they do group or pair projects and presentations. In fact, everyone benefits as the students see their curriculum come alive to address issues in the classrooms, across subject areas, in the school as a whole, as well as in the community. It is assumed that the greater the level of integration desired, the higher the level of collaboration required in multidisciplinary instruction.

Advantages of multidisciplinary

Improve communication ability

Get acquainted with the collaborative process of product development

Foster collaboration skills.

Positively beneficial for future career development

Different professions complement each other

Disadvantages:

Time pressure and

Differences in background

Interdisciplinary and curriculum:

It involves the combining of two or more academic discipline into one activity. Theories that cut across disciplines and highlight the process and meaning rather than combining different discipline contents (Odeh et al., 2017). For example, the design of a medical device requires engineering skills as well as the knowledge of a specific human organ’s function.

Interdisciplinary education has a role crucial role in science teaching, because it supplies new resources for the progress of science and technology. Fields such as medical physics, biochemistry, bio engineering, physical chemistry, just to mention some are valid proof of the need for interaction between sciences. The purpose of interdisciplinary approach is to dissolve the boundaries of various areas of study and encourage learning across the curriculum. The key factors of an interdisciplinary education are the application, association integration and transfer of knowledge. Learning skill in isolation is not a viable approach in modern education. Though interdisciplinary teaching the students can experience the applicative part of what they are learning and also see the value of it. Together with the constructive and critical thinking, effective learning is encouraged as well .Both the undergraduate and postgraduate students encounter frequent gaps in their knowledge because of the lack of coordination and interaction between disciplines. This hiccup in the educational system is overcome by could be overcome through a better organization of curriculum.

Need

Education helps the individual to gain knowledge about particular discipline that develops student’s capacity to analyze information and apply it to daily life situation. To improve students’ understanding and make the learning process more productive and enjoyable, they need to experience the connection between different subjects of the respective curriculum.

Engaging students and helping them to develop knowledge, insights, problem solving skills, self-confidence, self-efficacy, and a passion for learning are common goals that educators bring to the classroom and interdisciplinary and instruction and exploration promotes realization of these objectives.

Advantages of interdisciplinary approach

- Students are highly motivated as they have a vested interest in pursuing topics that are interesting to them. As a result, the content is often rooted in life experiences, giving an

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authentic purpose for the learning and connecting it to a real world context. Consequently, the learning becomes meaningful, purposeful and deeper resulting in learning experiences that stay with the student for a lifetime.

- Students cover topics in more depth because they are considering the many and varied perspectives from which a topic can be explored.
- Critical thinking skills are used and developed as students look across disciplinary boundaries to consider other viewpoints and also begin to compare and contrast concepts across subject areas.
- Students begin to consolidate learning by synthesizing ideas from many perspectives and consider an alternative way of acquiring knowledge.
- Exploring topics across a range of subject boundaries motivates students to pursue new knowledge in different subject areas.
- Transferable skills of critical thinking, synthesis and research are developed and are applicable to future learning experiences.
- Interdisciplinary knowledge and application of different disciplines can lead to greater creativity.
- Worthwhile topics of research can fall in the ‘spaces’ between the traditional disciplines.

Conclusion:

Interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary as innovative methods of teaching helps in the development of knowledge related to the two or more academic discipline and also develops the ability of problem solving critical thinking and makes the learner to acquaint with the present and future needs of the society. This paper gives emphasizes on the use of innovative teaching methods in the teaching learning process .For this the content has to be organized and teachers are trained in use of interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary approach in teaching to make science teaching more interesting and enjoyable.

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Hsien-Hui Tang, Emily Hsiao

National Taiwan University of Science and Technology, drhhtang@mail.ntust.edu.tw

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